

Edit Distance Algorithm to Increase Storage Efficiency of Javanese Corpora

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Abstract—Since the one-to-one word translator does not have the facility to translate pragmatic aspects of Javanese, the parallel text alignment model described uses a phrase pair combination. The algorithm aligns the parallel text automatically from the beginning to the end of each sentence. Even though the results of the phrase pair combination outperform the previous algorithm, it is still inefficient. Recording all possible combinations consume more space in the database and time consuming. The original algorithm is modified by applying the edit distance coefficient to improve the data-storage efficiency. As a result, the data-storage consumption is 90% reduced as well as its learning period (42s).

Keywords—edit distance coefficient, Javanese, parallel text alignment, phrase pair combination

I. INTRODUCTION

LANGUAGE is recognised as one of a nation cultural identity. It is used to communicate with others as well as media in art. The language is categorised as endangered language when the use of it is uncommon. For example Javanese, one among traditional languages in Indonesia which is used improperly by its million users, especially teenagers. Javanese has a complex sub system which is called levels of speech. The levels are focused on how to communicate with others based on the attributes of subject and object of the utterance. The attributes are age difference, social status and relationships between speaker and interlocutor. Javanese speech levels can be related to the traditional performance which used the language to deliver goodness. People may be unable to learn morality from the art, unless they understand the language. Consequently, improper use of speech levels is not only dangerous to the language existence but is also harmful to Javanese culture.

In means of saving endangered languages by using technology, an Artificial Javanese Intelligent Tutor (AJI-Tutor) is currently in development [1]. In the first stage of AJI-Tutor development, a simple bilingual translator was created as the foundation of the politeness agent of the system.

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However, that translator utilised a single (one-to-one) word translation system which was unable to translate Javanese properly since the language has pragmatic meaning realised through particular combinations of words.

The pragmatic competence, an ability to understand the accurate expression and interpretation of intended meaning [2], is a complicating factor in translation. In order to cope with that factor, The next development of the translation is based on the research that phrase based alignment as an enhanced option to form bilingual corpora for translation knowledge base because of its accuracy and flexibility[3],[4]. The results produced are better than the single word alignment algorithm as all pair combinations are recorded. However, the knowledge base produced by the algorithm may become inefficient due to a rich corpus which consists of large structured sets of texts [5]. The greater trained parallel text consumes more space in the database as make the searching process become slower. In this paper, we modify the Javanese automatic parallel text alignment to increase the efficiency of the database.

II. JAVANESE TRANSLATION MODELLING

Javanese linguists [6-8] classify the speech levels into three levels *krama*, *madya* and *ngoko*. *Ngoko* (Ng) is a casual speech, used between friends and close family. *Madya* (Md) is everyday speech used between villagers, and *krama* (Kr) is refined, formal speech used with and by high-status people. The three levels of politeness effectively constitute different dialects, albeit with similar grammars. Since aligning a single word with only one word in another level is often unfeasible, the language must be aligned in a pair combination; that is, a lexical and pragmatic combination.

TABLE I
EXAMPLES OF JAVANESE LEXICAL TRANSLATION

bahasa Indonesia	ngoko	krama	English meaning
<i>ibuku</i>	<i>ibuku</i>	<i>ibu kula</i>	<i>my mother</i>
<i>mengapa</i>	<i>geneya</i>	<i>kening menapa</i>	<i>why</i>
<i>hari libur</i>	<i>Prei</i>	<i>prei</i>	<i>a holiday</i>
<i>kita</i>	<i>awake dhewe</i>	<i>kita</i>	<i>us</i>
<i>kuda</i>	<i>Jaran</i>	<i>turangga</i>	<i>a horse</i>
<i>sama</i>	<i>padha</i>	<i>sami</i>	<i>equal</i>

The lexical combination is created based on the unique translation of Javanese words. When transforming the language literally, one *krama* word may change into two words (1:2) at other speech levels; the same applies to *bahasa Indonesia*, and vice versa (2:1). Furthermore, the reverse combination must be provided if the translation direction is changed. However, a single word alignment (1:1) is still covered to accommodate the translation of one single word to another single word, as shown in Table I.

The pragmatic combination is modelled to align particular pairs. Referring to Javanese subject-verb agreement (SVA) [9], the verb may change based on who is the subject of the action. The example in Table 2 shows how a verb employed in speech may be totally different depending on the social status or age of the subjects. This fact needs to be accommodated.

TABLE II
EXAMPLE OF PRAGMATIC PAIR ALIGNMENT

Action (<i>ngoko</i>)	Higher status subject (father)	Lower status subject (young brother)
sleeping (<i>tururu</i>)	<i>bapak tururu (Ng)</i> <i>bapak sare (Kr)</i>	<i>adik tururu (Ng)</i> <i>adik tilem (Kr)</i>
talking (<i>omong</i>)	<i>bapak omong (Ng)</i> <i>bapak ngendika (Kr)</i>	<i>adik omong (Ng)</i> <i>adik matur (Kr)</i>
eating (<i>mangan</i>)	<i>bapak mangan (Ng)</i> <i>bapak dhahar (Kr)</i>	<i>adik mangan (Ng)</i> <i>adik nedha (Kr)</i>
taking a bath (<i>adus</i>)	<i>bapak adus (Ng)</i> <i>bapak siram (Kr)</i>	<i>adik adus (Ng)</i> <i>adik adus (Kr)</i>

Both pragmatic and lexical pair combinations (P) are then modelled as follows.

$$P \begin{cases} (n_i, 0, k_j, 0): \text{single word pair (1:1)} \\ (0, n_i, k_j, k_{j+1}): \text{one - two pair (1:2)} \\ (n_i, n_{i+1}, 0, k_j): \text{two - one pair (2:1)} \\ (n_i, n_{i+1}, k_j, k_{j+1}): \text{two - two pair (2:2)} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

III. THE JAVANESE AUTOMATIC PAIRED BI-TEXT ALIGNMENT

Basically, the Javanese automatic paired bi-text alignment consists of two processes, text parsing and phrase combination alignment. The results then recorded into the database as shows in Fig 1.

Fig. 1 Javanese automatic paired bi-text alignment

A. The Database

The database is designed to store and manage the data (Fig. 2). It consists of two tables of words (WINA and WKrm) and two phrase tables (PINA and PKrm) to record unique words and phrases in both languages. The primary key of word tables is the ID_word (ID_INA and ID_Krm) that is an auto increment integer. The combination of two ID_words in phrase tables can be considered as primary key of such tables because of its uniqueness. The contents of these four tables are the results of parsing process. Afterwards, the parsing data will be stored as pairs in the Table of pairs. Furthermore, the frequency of word, phrase and pair is recorded in the database during the related procedures.

Fig. 2 Database design

B. The text parsing algorithm

The text parsing stage is a monolingual process, where every text divided into sentences then parsed into a list of words. Based on definitions and models explained before, punctuation still used as the separator between sentences as well as the space to distinct words. The training data is the parallel text which parsed using the modified parsing algorithm as shows in Fig.3.

Fig. 3 The parsing process

After words identified, the availability of the words will be checked in the database. If the database is empty, the word will be classified as a new one, then stored and automatically indexed. The frequency of such a word also recorded because the value will be applied in the translation process. However, when the system found that the specific word had been inserted, the frequency will be updated without any changing to the words' order in the database.

Two arrays created to substitute and simplify the bilingual text. The rows indicated the i^{th} sentence in the monolingual text while columns represented j^{th} word in every sentence. The content of arrays is the word's index as substitution of the related word in the database. For example, the sentence *ayahku tidur* recorded as 1 and 2 in an array of *bahasa Indonesia* which will be implemented in the automatic alignment process.

C. The phrase combination alignment

Providing knowledge for the bilingual translation in form word or phrase pairs is the aim of parallel text alignment. The pairs are bilingually composed from arrays of *krama* (K) and *bahasa Indonesia* (B). The first stage is checking the equality of the number of sentences in both arrays. If the number is unequal, the minimum value procedure will choose the lowest array as a reference of the alignment. When the number of sentences is equal, matrix are ready to arrange into pairs.

Fig. 4 Pair combinations illustration

The next step is pairing the matrix elements based on lexical and pragmatic pair combinations (1). For example, one element of K will be coupled with single element of B (1:1). The pair will be recorded as a new data as well as its frequency (F_{pair}). Contrary, if existed pair found, the system will only update the frequency of the related pair. Those procedures are repeated from the beginning to the end of the particular row of the matrix, represent a sentence. The iteration for one type pair combination will stop after processing the last sentence in the parallel matrix. Afterwards, the alignment process will be repeated for the rest combinations (Fig. 4). The flowchart in Fig. 5 illustrates the whole process of the automatic bilingual alignment.

Fig. 5 Pair alignment process

D. Testing results

The result covers all possible combinations based on the highest frequency of the pair as the accepted alignment. The other combinations are not deleted because they may come to constitute a proper alignment when the quantity of training data is increased. The alignment results should be more accurate if the number of examples is extended since it is based on the occurrence frequency of the word and phrase pair in the sentence.

TABLE III
ALIGNMENT RESULTS FOR VARIOUS PARALLEL TEXTS

Total words	number of sentence s	mean of words/sentence	pairs formed	learning period (s)	
Kr	Ina				
8	10	4	2	43	7
253	235	36	7	7800	344
828	855	105	7	31612	4805

However, when the number of examples is increased (Table 3), the number of pair combinations increase as well as the learning time. Furthermore, the length and complexity of the sentence may prolong the learning iteration. As presented by Table 3, a huge difference between total words in the training data and the corresponding pair combinations shows that the proper alignments are mixed with the unintended ones.

IV. STORAGE EFFICIENCY BY USING SHIFTING DISTANCE COEFFICIENT

The automatic alignment records all combinations in the knowledge base. However, when the sentences become long and complex, recording of all possible pairs of the phrase is not efficient. The main reason is that the process to form the alignment candidate may consume time and lead to a large database. In order to increase the learning efficiency and to reduce data storage consumption, shifting distance coefficient (D) is proposed. The shifting distance is set in every alignment combination of *krama* (K) and *bahasa Indonesia* (B) to limit the iteration, as shown in the pseudo code below.

```

for each sentence in bahasa Indonesia
for c:= i - D to i + D do
  if (c>0) and (c<=K[j,0])
    then
      P{(bi,0,kj,0):one-one,(0,bi,kj,kj+1}): one-two,
        (bi,bi+1,0,kj):two-one, (bi,bi+1,kj,kj+1}):two-two}
      check the database
      if the combination is unavailable in database
        then
          record the pair combination with its frequency
        else update the frequency of the pair
      end if
    end for
  end for

```

Iteration limit will be changed by adjusting the shifting distance (Fig. 6). While the coefficient is set to zero, any word or phrase in *krama* is paired with another equally indexed chunk in *bahasa Indonesia*. As pictured by Fig 3, if $D=0$, the result of the 1:2 pair combination is $P \{(b_2,0,k_2,k_3)\}$. When the coefficient tuned to one, the iteration will start from one word before (i-1) then ended in one after the reference word (i+1). As a result, the pair extended to $P \{(b_2,0,k_1,k_2), (b_2,0,k_2,k_3), (b_2,0,k_3,k_4)\}$ for just the 1:2 combination. Therefore, the original combination, for instance, $P \{(b_2,0,k_1,k_2), (b_2,0,k_2,k_3), (b_2,0,k_3,k_4), \dots, (b_2,0,k_{n-1},k_n)\}$ is simplified to speed up the process and to save the data space.

A bilingual short story is used to evaluate the efficiency of implementing shifting distance coefficient in the automatic alignment algorithm. The parallel text consists of long and complex sentences, 25 words per sentence. Table 4 shows that the number of words between texts is unequal which means some single word may be translated into more than one in another language. The total words and the number of unique words are measured then stored in the database. The average word's frequency and the average number of words in a sentence are calculated by dividing the total words with the number of unique words and the number of sentences correspondingly.

Fig. 6 Pairing bilingual words (2:1) in various shifting distance (D)

TABLE IV
DETAILS OF PARALLEL TEXT

Text details	<i>Krama</i>	<i>Bahasa Indonesia</i>
total words	253	235
the number of unique words	164	159
the average of word's frequency	2	1

the number of sentences	36	36
the maximum words in a sentence	25	25
the average number of words in a sentence	7	7

$$E_d = \frac{\max PC - PC_d}{\max PC} \quad (2)$$

Afterwards, the bilingual text is automatically aligned by tuning various values of shifting distance coefficient (Table 12). The formed pair candidates (PC_d) and the learning period (t_d) are measured during the alignment process. The maximum quantity of PC is used as reference to measure the storage efficiency (E). The efficiency calculates by dividing the difference between pair candidates with the value of the reference number (2).

TABLE V
RESULTS OF BI-TEXT ALIGNMENT WITH VARIOUS SHIFTING DISTANCE COEFFICIENT

D	Pair candidates (PC_d)	Learning period (t_d)	Storage efficiency (E_d)
0	783	42	0.9
1	2164	105	0.72
2	3345	155	0.57
n	7800	344	0

From Table V, we can conclude that the standard coefficient $D=0$ can align the parallel text fastest (42 seconds) and increase (0.9) the data-storage efficiency. In other words, the smallest coefficient D provides the quickest learning period and the most efficient data storage. However, setting D to its minimum value should be avoided in order to prevent the loss of potential pairs recorded during the training progress. The suggested value of the shifting distance coefficient is one due to the rule of the Javanese translation that one Javanese word may be translated into two words in different levels of speech.

V. CONCLUSION

The original Javanese parallel text alignment is modified in order to increase the data-storage efficiency. As a result, the storage efficiency is increased (90%) by applying shifting distance coefficient to the alignment algorithm. In consequence, the application of the coefficient can boost the speed of the learning process by cutting the number of iteration in each sentence. The modified algorithm may contribute to the next development of the Javanese pragmatic translation which will be consisting of at least five languages, *bahasa Indonesia*, *ngoko*, *ngoko alus*, *krama* and *krama alus* [10].

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